

EFFECT OF DAMAGE DUE TO THERMAL SHOCK CYCLING AND HYGROTHERMAL AGEING ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF GFRP-AI SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

In the present investigation, the effect of thermal shock cycling and hygrothermal ageing of a glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) and a Al- GFRP sandwich structure on their flexural behavior has been studied. In addition the skin-core interfacial load distribution along the length of the sandwich structure was analytically studied by using a theoretical model previously developed by the authors.

Keywords: thermal shock cycling, hygrothermal ageing, modeling.

INTRODUCTION

In aeronautical applications, structural components can be submitted to both mechanical loads and large cyclic temperature variations. Also, composites in aeronautical and marine applications are subject to large cyclic temperature variations and/or to long term immersion in water. The damage produced and the mechanical degradation due to both factors (thermal cycling and water absorption) is a very complex phenomenon and a detailed analysis is needed.

Due to the structural heterogeneity of the composite the fatigue damage process is rather complex, and consists of a variety of damage modes such as matrix cracking, debonding between fiber and matrix, fiber fracture or delamination between plies. The overall damage history depends on the material constituents, on the loading history and on the composite structure. Woven GFRP composite materials are extensively used in a wide range of industries, including aerospace structures, infrastructures and others, which are frequently designed to carry static and fatigue loads. Due to the presence of polymer matrix, woven composites may exhibit significant viscoelastic behavior. Further, the ultimate failure loads may also depend on the time period over which the load is applied. Engineering designs based on static properties without considering time dependent degradation of composite materials may lead to and eventually cause catastrophic disaster.

Under thermal loading, large stresses may develop in polymer composite due to the mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansion of the fibres and the matrix, at a microscopic level, and consequently of adjacent plies stacked with different orientations

in the laminate. It appears that one of the most severe problems concerning the survivability of most composites is the bond breakage between their constituents. Such a breakage is caused by either extension of pre-existing cracks or by the creation of new cracks at the material interfaces. For example, upon thermal or mechanical loading of the composite, micro-stresses will develop at the interface between various constituents. If these stresses exceed the corresponding bonding strength of the composite they will result in crack formation. Such interface cracking is the earliest form of damage frequently observed in composite structures.

Many researchers have investigated thermal cycling shock on different composites materials [1-8] while the effect of hygrothermal ageing on different composites materials was studied by several other researchers [9-17].

In the present investigation, the effect of thermal shock cycling and hygrothermal ageing of polymer composite (GFRP) and of sandwich structures (GFRP-Al) on their flexural behavior has been studied. In addition, the interfacial stress distribution along the skin-core interfacial length was evaluated and analyzed by means of a theoretical model not for both the undamaged and the damaged materials due to thermal shock cycling and hygrothermal ageing.

MATERIALS

The sandwich beam face sheets (skins) were aluminum sheets 100 mm length, 12 mm wide and 1mm thick with bending modulus equal to 63.4 ± 0.3 GPa. The core material used in this study was 40 layers of glass fabric 80gsm with a layer thickness of 0.05 mm in a $0^\circ / 90^\circ$ fibre orientation, 100 mm length, 12 mm wide and 2 mm thick. The fiber volume fraction was 60 %. Finally, the adhesive used to bond the face sheets to the core was epoxy resin LF (lamination resin for aircraft construction). Epoxy resin LF is a bisphenol A resin. It has been approved by the German federal aviation authority for the construction of powered aircraft and gliders in conjunction with glass, aramid and carbon fibers. The hardener used for the resin was LF 1 which is a fast amine hardener for smaller components, glued joints, and repairs in aircraft construction. The resin compound cures at room temperature in 24 hours. After this preliminary period of curing, aircraft parts must be hot-cured for a further fifteen hours at 50-55 °C.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

a) **Thermal Fatigue:** The minimum temperature was set to be -27 °C and the maximum one was set to 50 °C. Each cycle had to last long enough for the specimens to reach a thermal equilibrium state. After some preliminary tests it was found that 10 minutes in the freezer and 10 minutes in the oven were adequate for reaching thermal equilibrium state. The number of thermal cycles applied was: 1, 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100, 120, 140 and 160.

b) **Hygrothermal Ageing:** In addition, hygrothermal ageing took place in a bath with distilled water at 40 °C for 0, 2, 8, 24, 28, 32, 48, 52, 56, 120, 240, 480, 960 and 1920 h for both core and sandwich structures. A standard procedure of water uptake was followed. Before placing the test specimens into the water bath specimens were dried in an oven at 50 °C, until their weight loss was stabilized. The dried specimens were then placed in a high vacuum for 24 h to create full-dried specimens and their weights were

measured with an analytical balance. Then the specimens were immersed in distilled-water bath at constant temperature of 40 °C, controlled to ± 0.5 °C. The specimens, conditioned in water, were then removed at the already mentioned immersion times, wiped, air dried for 5 minutes, and then weighed. All specimens were weighted before and after the water absorption procedure with ± 0.001 gr accuracy. The thus conditioned specimens were then subjected to three point bending experiments.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Bending tests were performed at room temperature, on the thus conditioned test specimens. Bending measurements were carried out with a conventional Instron type tester (INSTRON 4301), at room temperature (25 °C). Specimens with a gauge length of 63 mm were tested at a constant strain rate of 1 mm/min.

THEORETICAL APPROACH

To elucidate the significance of the interface stiffness concept on the skin-core interface load distribution in FRP-metal laminate beams G.C.Papanicolaou et al. [18] proposed a shear lag model, which can be used for the determination of the load distribution along the skin-core interface length of FRP-metal laminates subjected to in – plane tension. The model introduces a basic hypothesis according which, the interface stiffness depends on the difference in shear moduli of the constituent materials as well as on the degree of adhesion which, in turn, depends on the abrupt jump in shear moduli at the skin–core boundary.

According to the model, the interfacial axial force developed along the length of the core material is given by:

$$N_C = \frac{P}{\left(\frac{1}{E_S A_S} + \frac{1}{E_C A_C}\right)} \cdot \frac{1}{\sinh nL} \cdot [(\sinh nx) + \sinh n(L-x)] \cdot \left(\frac{f}{E_C A_C} - \frac{(1-f)}{E_S A_S}\right) + \frac{\sinh(nL)}{E_S A_S} \quad (1)$$

where: P is the external force applied to the beam, E_S is the skin modulus, E_C is the core modulus, A_S is the total facing cross-area, A_C is the total core cross-area, L is the total length, f is a constant ($0 < f < 1$) representing the percentage of the force P transferred to the facing, as well as to the core and n is a constant calculated as follows:

$$n^2 = K \left(\frac{1}{E_C A_C} + \frac{1}{E_S A_S}\right).$$

Next, the shear load per unit length can be calculated as follows:

$$t = \frac{dN_C}{dx} = \frac{Pn}{\left(\frac{1}{E_S A_S} + \frac{1}{E_C A_C}\right)} \cdot \frac{1}{\sinh nL} \left[(\cosh nx - \cosh n(L-x)) \cdot \left(\frac{f}{E_C A_C} - \frac{(1-f)}{E_S A_S}\right) \right] \quad (2)$$

Finally, the axial interfacial force along the length of the facings is given by:

$$N_S = P \left[1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{E_S A_S} + \frac{1}{E_C A_C} \right) \cdot \sinh(nL)} \cdot \left[\sinh(nx) + \sinh n(L-x) \right] \cdot \left[\frac{f}{E_C A_C} - \frac{1-f}{E_S A_S} \right] + \frac{\sinh(nL)}{E_S A_S} \right] \quad (3)$$

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

a) **Degradation due to Thermal Fatigue:** Figures 1 and 2 show the variation of the flexural strength and modulus respectively for both the core and the sandwich structure as a function of thermal shock cycle's number. It can be observed that there is a small variation of the core strength with thermal shock cycle's number while no such effect on the sandwich strength is observed. In addition, flexural strength for the core material is always higher than the respective one of the sandwich structures. On the other hand, a small variation of the flexural modulus with thermal shock number of cycles is observed. In all cases, sandwich modulus is higher than the respective one for the core material.

A representative stress-strain curve for both the core and the sandwich structure after 60 thermal shock cycles is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that sandwich structure shows a more ductile behavior when compared with the core material.

b) **Degradation due to Hygrothermal Fatigue:** Figure 4 shows the percentage variation of the absorbed water with immersion time for both the core and the sandwich structure at 40 °C. Due to skin-core anomalous water absorption mechanisms, water absorption behavior in the sandwich structure initially increases reaching a maximum value and the peak value is followed by a subsequent decrease. In contrary, a continuous increase of water absorption for the core material is observed. The variation of the flexural modulus for both the core and the sandwich structure with immersion time is presented in Figure 5. For all immersion times core material is characterised by higher values of flexural strength than those of for the sandwich structure. This kind of behaviour is reversed in the case of modulus variation (Figure 6).

APPLICATION OF THE THEORETICAL MODEL FOR THE UNDAMAGED MATERIAL

The shear lag model presented above was applied in all three cases; i.e. for the undamaged material, the damaged material due to thermal shock cycles and finally the damaged material due to hygrothermal fatigue and results concerning load distribution along the length of the skin-core interface are shown in Figures 7-12, 13-14 and 15-16 respectively. Results are summarised in the following conclusions.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present investigation, the mechanical behaviour after hygrothermal fatigue and thermal shock cycling of both GFRP and Al-GFRP sandwich structures was studied. In order to specify with higher accuracy the performance of damaged and undamaged polymer composite, a simple analytical model for the estimation of the skin-core interfacial stress distribution and its variation with immersion time and with thermal cycle's number for both types of materials was applied.

The main conclusions are:

- There is a small variation of the core strength with thermal shock cycle's number while no such effect on the sandwich strength is observed.
- In addition, flexural strength for the core material is always higher than the respective one of the sandwich structures.
- On the other hand, a small variation of the flexural modulus with thermal shock number of cycles is observed.
- In all cases, sandwich modulus is higher than the respective one for the core material.
- Due to skin-core interfacial water absorption mechanisms, water absorption behavior in the sandwich structure initially increases reaching a maximum value and the peak value is followed by a subsequent decrease.
- In contrary, a continuous increase of water absorption for the core material is observed.
- For all immersion times core material is characterised by higher values of flexural strength than those of for the sandwich structure.
- This kind of behaviour is reversed in the case of modulus variation
- The shear-lag model applied is a simple analytical model, for the determination of the skin-core interfacial stress distribution for the undamaged and the damaged specimens due to water immersion or thermal shock cycling.
- According to the model predictions, the axial forces developed in both the core and the skin material do not change significantly with either the number of applied thermal shock cycles or with immersion time.
- The same observation is also valid for the interfacial shear stresses with some exception for the specimen's edges.

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Fig.1: Variation of the flexural strength with number of thermal shock cycles.

Fig.3: Stress-strain curves for the core and the sandwich material after 60 thermal shock cycles.

Fig.2: Variation of the flexural modulus with with number of thermal shock cycles.

Fig.4: Variation of percentage of absorbed water with immersion time for both the core and the sandwich material.

Fig.5: Variation of flexural strength with immersion time for both the core and the sandwich material .

Fig.6: Variation of flexural modulus with immersion time for both the core and the sandwich material.

Fig.7: Variation of N_S along the FRP metal laminate length for different K-values.

Fig.8: Variation of $N_{S_{max}}$ with K.

Fig.9: Variation of N_C along the FRP metal laminate length for different K-values.

Fig.10: Variation of $N_{C_{min}}$ with K.

Fig.11: Variation of the shear flow, t , along the FRP metal laminate length for different K-values.

Fig.12: Variation of t_{max} with K.

Fig.13: Variation of N_c along the FRP metal laminate length for fifteen different periods of thermal shock cycling (from $-27\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Fig.14: Variation of N_s along the FRP metal laminate length for fifteen different periods of thermal cycling shock (from $-27\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Fig.15: Variation of the shear flow t along the FRP metal laminate length for fifteen different periods of thermal shock cycling.

Fig.16: Variation of N_C along the FRP metal laminate length with immersion time.

Fig.17: Variation of N_s along the FRP metal laminate length with immersion time.

Fig.18: Variation of the shear flow along the FRP metal laminate length with immersion time.